

Development of repair solution for fatigue cracks using self-prestressing Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches

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ABSTRACT

A repair solution for fatigue cracks in steel structures using adhesively bonded iron-based shape memory alloy (Fe-SMA) strips and carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) sheets (Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches) was developed. The patches can self-prestress through an activation process (a heating and cooling process). An experimental study was conducted, wherein cracked steel plates were repaired with the Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches, and fatigue tests were performed. Test results showed that the Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches prolonged the fatigue life of cracked steel plates by more than 5 times, and in some cases a complete crack arrest was achieved.

KEYWORDS

Fatigue; Repair; Prestress; Fe-Mn-Si shape memory alloy; Memory Steel; Adhesively bonded.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue cracking is a common problem for steel structures. Many techniques have been developed to repair cracks, for example, drilling stop holes and using bonded carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) patches. Bonded CFRP patches have many advantages, such as non-destructive and lightweight characteristics, and excellent corrosion resistance (Teng et al., 2012). Various experimental studies have shown the effectiveness of bonded CFRP patches in repairing fatigue cracks in steel structures (Chen et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2009; Yu & Wu, 2018; Yu et al., 2013). Furthermore, prestressed repair solutions are desirable for fatigue cracks as they create a compressive stress field around the crack, effectively reducing the stress intensity factor, such that fatigue crack propagation was retarded or even completely arrested (Hosseini et al., 2017; Hosseini et al., 2019). However, the application of prestressed CFRP involves a tensioning process using bulky mechanical devices such as hydraulic jacks, which hinders the development of small-sized prestressed CFRP patches that are suitable for crack repair.

Recently, shape memory alloy (SMA) materials have been exploited for a prestressed repair. By utilizing the shape memory effect, the prestressing can be realized through an activation process (i.e., a heating and cooling process), which is easier than a mechanical tensioning process. Researchers have developed a patching system consisting of nickel-titanium-based shape memory alloy (NiTi-SMA) wires and CFRP sheets, and experimental tests indicated that the solution was effective (Abdy et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2018; Zheng & Dawood, 2017).

In addition to NiTi-SMAs, iron-based shape memory alloy (Fe-SMA) is very attractive owing to its excellent mechanical properties, high recovery stress, and lower manufacturing cost (Cladera et al., 2014). Izadi et al. (Izadi et al., 2018) developed a strengthening system wherein Fe-SMA strips were anchored to cracked steel plates through mechanical clamps and activated using an electrical resistive heating technique. Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2021) investigated repair solutions using adhesively bonded Fe-SMA strips on cracked steel plates. For steel plates strengthened with bonded non-prestressed CFRP, bonded non-prestressed Fe-SMA, and bonded Fe-SMA strips activated using a heat gun, the fatigue lives were extended for 1.70, 2.61, and 3.51 times, respectively (Wang et al., 2021). Additionally, as

the bonded joints are the foundation of the successful application of bonded Fe-SMA strips, Li et al. (Li, Chatzi, et al., 2023; Li, Wang, et al., 2023) experimentally studied the behavior of the Fe-SMA-to-steel bonded joints and proposed a semi-analytical and semi-numerical model to predict the behavior.

The previous studies outlined here have demonstrated the promising potential of CFRP sheets and Fe-SMA strips for fatigue crack repair. In this study, a bonded patch that combines the Fe-SMA strips and CFRP sheets (hereafter referred to as Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patch) is investigated. The repair procedures mainly consisted of three steps: bonding Fe-SMA strips, activation of Fe-SMA, and bonding CFRP sheets. The design concept is that the activated Fe-SMA strip can offer both stiffness and prestress, while the CFRP sheet can provide additional stiffness and protection for the prestressed Fe-SMA against corrosions. Five specimens were prepared, including one reference and four specimens repaired with the Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches, and fatigue tests were performed to evaluate their performances.

MATERIALS

Fe-SMA strip

The Fe-SMA strips (with a chemical composition of Fe–17Mn–5Si–10Cr–4Ni–1(V, C)) used in this study were provided by re-fer AG, Switzerland. The Fe-SMA strips were prestrained to 2% in the factory and then delivered to the site. Figure 1a shows the mechanical properties of the Fe-SMA. The Fe-SMA strip had an elastic modulus of approximately 164 GPa, an ultimate tensile strength of 1042 MPa, and a nominal thickness of 1.5 mm. Figure 1b shows the recovery stress behavior of the Fe-SMA, wherein the Fe-SMA samples were rigidly fixed at both ends and heated up to the target activation temperatures and then cooled down to the room temperature. For different activation temperatures ranging from 100 to 350 °C, the recovery stress of the Fe-SMA varied in a range of approximately 220 to 380 MPa.

Figure 1: (a) Stress–strain curves of the prestrained Fe-SMA strip. (b) Recovery stress at different activation temperatures. (the graphs are reproduced from (Gu et al., 2021; Wang et al.)).

CFRP sheet

The CFRP sheet used in the study was S&P C-sheet 240 (200 g/m²), which was unidirectional carbon fiber fabrics. The CFRP sheet has an elastic modulus of approximately 240 GPa, an ultimate tensile strength of 4400 MPa, and a nominal thickness of 0.113 mm (*S&P C-sheet 240 technical data sheet (CSheet240.TDS.EU-EN.V2)*).

Steel plates

Steel plates with an elastic modulus of 205 GPa, a yield strength of 421 MPa, and an ultimate strength of 526 MPa, were used in the tests (Hosseini et al., 2017).

Adhesives

SikaPower-1277

A two-component epoxy adhesive SikaPower-1277 was employed for bonding Fe-SMA to steel plates. SikaPower-1277 has an elastic modulus of approximately 2 GPa, a lap-shear strength of 28 MPa, and a glass transition temperature (T_g) of approximately 67 °C (*SikaPower-1277 Product data sheet*, 2018). In addition, the adhesive exhibits no degradation in its shear strength after exposure to a temperature of 180 °C for 1 h and cooling to the room temperature (*Additional product information: Material properties of SikaPower-1277*, 2018), which indicates the safe temperatures that can be applied to the adhesive during activation.

S&P Resin 55 HP

A two-component epoxy resin adhesive S&P Resin 55 HP that is mating with the S&P C-sheet 240 was used in the wet lay-up process of CFRP sheets. S&P Resin 55 HP has an elastic modulus of ≥ 3.2 GPa, a lap-shear strength of ≥ 50 MPa, and a glass transition temperature of 53 °C (*S&P Resin 55 HP technical data sheet (Resin55HP.TDS.EU-EN.V3)*).

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental program was to investigate the repair effect of Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches. Table 1 lists the specimens in the study. Steel plates with a dimension of 850×150×10 mm, which had a central notch and precracks of approximately 1 mm were involved (Figure 2a). The three main steps of the repair process were bonding Fe-SMA strips, activation of Fe-SMA, and bonding CFRP sheets, as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

The Fe-SMA strips were bonded to steel plates using adhesive SikaPower-1277 (Figure 3a). The Fe-SMA strips had a width of 50 mm and a thickness of 1.5 mm, whereas various lengths (i.e., 100, 200, 300, and 500 mm) were involved, as listed in Table 1. Before bonding, both the surfaces of the Fe-SMA strips and steel plates were cleaned and sandblasted.

The activation of the Fe-SMA was conducted through the electrical resistive heating technique after the specimens curing for more than one week. Figure 2c and Figure 3b show the setup and instrumentations for the activation. Four copper connectors were attached to the Fe-SMA strips by insulated G-clamps. A computer-controlled electric power supply provided a current through the Fe-SMA strips on both sides which were connected as a series circuit. The activation length was the middle half of the Fe-SMA strip (i.e., $L_{act} = L_{SMA}/2$) whereas the two ends were working as anchorage during activation. The Fe-SMA strips were heated to a target activation temperature of 180 °C.

During the activation, six thermocouples were mounted on the specimens, wherein T1–T2 and T4–T5 were mounted on the activation parts of the Fe-SMA strips on each side, respectively, T3 was mounted on the anchorage part of the Fe-SMA strip, whereas T6 was on the steel plate (Figure 2c). When the maximum measured temperature reached 180 °C, the power supply switched off automatically. Then the specimens were left to cool down to the room temperature through air cooling. Four strain gauges were mounted at the middle section on the steel plate to measure the strain (Figure 2c).

After the Fe-SMA was activated, a CFRP sheet was bonded on both sides of the steel plate, covering the Fe-SMA strip (Figure 3c). The dimensions of the CFRP sheets varied with the Fe-SMA strips with an additional 20 mm margin, such that the CFRP sheets had a width of 90 mm (i.e., $W_{CFRP} = W_{SMA} + 40$) and a length in the range of 140 to 540 mm (i.e., $L_{CFRP} = L_{SMA} + 40$), as listed in Table 1. Prior to bonding the CFRP, the surfaces of the steel plates to be bonded were sandblasted, and the surfaces of the Fe-SMA strips were grinded using sandpapers. The CFRP sheet saturated with the epoxy resin adhesive S&P Resin 55 HP was laid upon the Fe-SMA strip. After the wet lay-up process, the specimens cured for more than one week.

Here, patches with different Fe-SMA lengths were studied (Table 1), because a short patch length is desirable, whereas the bonded length is a critical role in the bonded capacity and the Fe-SMA prestress level. The feasibility of short patch lengths was investigated. On the other hand, for the widths of the

Fe-SMA strip and CFRP sheets as well as the number of layers of the CFRP sheets, they can be adjusted according to the required prestress and stiffness. Here, fixed widths and number of layers were adopted.

For the reference and strengthened specimens, fatigue tests were performed with the loading schemes as follows. The beach marking loading regime was employed (Figure 4). An interval of N_1 cycles of full-amplitude fatigue loading was applied, followed by an interval of N_2 cycles of half-amplitude fatigue loading while the maximum stress was kept constant, and such intervals ($N_1 + N_2$) were repeated. The crack propagation rate decreases substantially during the half-amplitude loading intervals, generating a different texture on the fracture surface. Such texture can be identified as marks which are formed at known cycles, so the crack length at a given number of fatigue cycles can be measured. In the fatigue test, N_1 and N_2 were 50,000 and 25,000, respectively.

Initially, a load level with the stress range of $\Delta\sigma=90$ MPa, stress ratio of $R=0.2$, and loading frequency of $f=15$ Hz was applied. If fatigue cracks propagated under the load level, the fatigue load was continued until specimen failure. Otherwise, if crack arrest was achieved, the load level was then increased to the stress range of $\Delta\sigma=105$ MPa while maintaining the stress ratio and frequency constant, and the specimen was loaded until failure. A strain gauge was mounted on the CFRP sheet to monitor the crack propagation (when the crack propagated, the measured strain increased, whereas if the measured strain maintained constant, it indicated the crack arrest).

Table 1: Test matrix

Specimens*	Strengthening	L_{SMA} (mm)	W_{SMA} (mm)	L_{act} (mm)	L_{CFRP} (mm)	W_{CFRP} (mm)
Reference	No	-	-	-	-	-
SC-100	Fe-SMA+CFRP	100	50	50	140	90
SC-200	Fe-SMA+CFRP	200	50	100	240	90
SC-300	Fe-SMA+CFRP	300	50	150	340	90
SC-500	Fe-SMA+CFRP	500	50	250	540	90

SC indicates strengthening with Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches, and the subsequent number indicates the length of the Fe-SMA (i.e., L_{SMA}).

Figure 2: Repair procedures. Unit: mm.

(a) Bonding Fe-SMA strip

(b) Activation of bonded Fe-SMA strip

(c) Bonding CFRP sheet

Figure 3: (a) Bonding Fe-SMA strip. (b) Activation of bonded Fe-SMA strip using electrical resistive heating method. (c) Bonding CFRP sheet.

Figure 4. Loading regime of the beach-marking technique.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Activation results

Figure 5a presents the typical temperatures history of the specimens during the activation, showing that the Fe-SMA was heated to the target temperature of 180 °C in approximately 20–60 s. Then the specimens were left to cool down to the room temperature for several hours. During the entire activation process, the maximum temperatures of the anchorage areas of all the specimens were 36–45 °C, lower than the glass transition temperature of adhesive SikaPower-1277 (i.e., 67 °C).

Figure 5b shows the average values of the final strain readings of the four strain gauges on the steel plates after activation. Compressive strains were observed, which indicated the presence of Fe-SMA prestress. The average strains were -67.5, -86.2, -103.4, and -123.1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$, respectively. An increased average compressive strain was observed when the activation length increased.

Figure 5: (a) Temperature history during activation of specimen SC-500. (b) Average strain of strain gauges on steel plates after activation.

Fatigue test results

Table 2 summarizes the fatigue test results. Figure 6 shows the typical failure modes and fracture surfaces of the repaired specimens after fatigue tests. The failure modes varied depending on the Fe-SMA length. For specimens SC-100 and SC-200, Fe-SMA debonding along with CFRP fracture and partial debonding were observed (Figure 6a). However, for specimens SC-300 and SC-500, Fe-SMA and CFRP fracture along with Fe-SMA and CFRP partial debonding were observed (Figure 6b). The main difference between the failure modes was that for specimens SC-100 and SC-200, Fe-SMA strips were pulled off the steel plates, whereas for specimens SC-300 and SC-500, Fe-SMA strips were fractured.

From the beach marks on the fracture surfaces, the fatigue crack growth behavior against the fatigue load cycles was obtained. Figure 7 summarizes the $a-N$ curves, where a was the crack length and N was the total count of the applied full-amplitude cycles. For specimen SC-100, crack arrest was achieved under the load level of $\Delta\sigma=90$ MPa (i.e., after applying 3.315×10^6 fatigue cycles, minimal change of the strain reading was observed). Thereafter, SC-100 was subjected to the increased load level of $\Delta\sigma=105$ MPa, and the specimen failure occurred after 1.167×10^6 cycles. For ease of calculation, the total fatigue life of SC-100 was taken as $(3.315+1.167)\times 10^6$ here. For the other specimens strengthened with the Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches, they failed under the load level of $\Delta\sigma=90$ MPa, whereas the fatigue lives were improved by 5.5 to 6.0 times, respectively, compared with the reference specimen.

All the repaired specimens substantially improved fatigue lives, which demonstrated the effectiveness of the repair solution. Moreover, the test results indicated that a compact patch with the Fe-SMA strip length being as short as 100 mm can still work effectively. Such small compact patches are highly desirable as they not only require less materials but are also more applicable in situations where available space is limited (e.g., for cracked details in orthotropic steel bridges and crane structures).

Table 2: Fatigue test results

Specimens	Stress range (MPa)	Applied effective cycles, N (million)	Fatigue life improvement	Observation
Reference	90	0.374	-	-
SC-100	90	3.315	-	Crack arrest
	105	1.167	12.0 *	Failure mode A **
SC-200	90	2.228	6.0	Failure mode A
SC-300	90	2.165	5.8	Failure mode B ***
SC-500	90	2.041	5.5	Failure mode B

* The total fatigue life compared with that of reference specimen, i.e., $12.0=(3.315+1.167)/0.374$

** Failure mode A: Fe-SMA debonding + CFRP fracture +CFRP partial debonding

*** Failure mode B: Fe-SMA and CFRP fracture + Fe-SMA and CFRP partial debonding

Failure mode A: Fe-SMA debonding + CFRP fracture +CFRP partial debonding
(a) SC-100

Failure mode B: Fe-SMA and CFRP fracture + Fe-SMA and CFRP partial debonding
(b) SC-300

Figure 6: Typical failure modes. (a) SC-100. (b) SC-300.

Figure 7: Fatigue crack growth behavior

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the repair solution for cracked steel plates using Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches was developed. Prestrained Fe-SMA strips were bonded over the cracks, and subsequently activated; furthermore, a layer of CFRP sheet was laid through wet lay-up process. The Fe-SMA strips were designed to provide stiffness and prestress, while the CFRP sheets were intended to further increase the stiffness and protect the Fe-SMA against environmental invasions. Fatigue tests of a reference and four repaired specimens were conducted. The following conclusions were drawn.

1. Bonded Fe-SMA strips with lengths from 100 to 500 mm were activated to 180 °C using the electric resistive heating technique. The prestress was successfully generated and sustained for all specimens, resulting in the average compressive strains of the steel plates ranging from -67.5 to -123.1 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$.
2. The fatigue lives of the precracked steel plates were substantially improved by the Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patches. After repair, the fatigue life extension ratios were more than 5.5, and crack arrest was achieved for specimen SC-100 under the load level of $\Delta\sigma=90$ MPa.
3. The effect of the Fe-SMA length on the performance of the repair solution was investigated. When the Fe-SMA length decreased from 500 mm to 100 mm, the final failure modes transferred from Fe-SMA fracture to debonding. However, the fatigue lives were not decreased with the decreased length, whereas specimen SC-100 showed the best performance.

This study demonstrates that the Fe-SMA/CFRP bonded patch can self-prestress itself successfully and it is a promising solution for repair of fatigue cracks. Moreover, the feasibility and effectiveness of small compact patches with clear advantages for applications in limited available space (e.g., orthotropic steel bridges and crane structures) are demonstrated.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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